

The bent and hyper-bent properties of a class of Boolean functions

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Abstract : This paper considers the bent and hyper-bent properties of a class of Boolean functions of the form $f^{(r)}_{a,b} = \mathrm{Tr}_1^n(ax^{r(2^m-1)}) + \mathrm{Tr}_1^4(bx^{\frac{2^n-1}{5}})$, where $n=2m$, $m \equiv 2k \pmod{4}$, $k \in \{0,1\}$, $a \in \mathbb{F}_{2^n}$ and $b \in \mathbb{F}_{16}$. When $m \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$, we present a detailed description for $f^{(r)}_{a,b}$ to be hyper-bent functions, and give a necessary condition for $f^{(r)}_{a,b}$ to be bent functions when $m \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$.

Keywords : Boolean functions, bent functions, hyper-bent functions, character sums

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